

The Role of Code-Mixing in Localizing the English Language: A Short Analysis of *Kanthapura*

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ABSTRACT

Code-Mixing have been used as an interesting strategy by the different writers across globe who either come from, or have an ancestral purchase upon, countries with a history of colonialism. As far as the Indo-Anglian literary pieces are concerned they too are embedded with this effective strategy. The prolonged contact between English and Indian languages, and its use by Indians with varied linguistic background and varying levels of competence in English, has resulted in it been 'Indianized'. This nativization or mother tongue word influence while writing in another language has now become the feature of their writing, but over a period of time this interference variety has accorded typical status and flavour to all the postcolonial writings. Raja Rao's novel '*Kanthapura*' (1938) is one such fictional but realistic account of how the great majority of people in India lived their lives under British rule and how they responded to the ideas and ideals of Indian nationalism. The novel has been considered by many to be the first classic modern Indian writing in English. In this novel Rao makes highly innovative use of the English language to fit it multilingual Indian society. The novelist's style of narration is best suited for the expression of Indian sensibility. Therefore, the text chosen for the study is to show how the author has used this sociolinguistic theory of code-mixing to unravel the Indian sensibility in his work.

Keywords: Bilingualism, Code-mixing, indianization, Indian English, *Kanthapura*

INTRODUCTION

Raja Rao's novel '*Kanthapura*' (1938) is the first major Indian novel in English. It is not merely a political novel, but a novel concerned as much with the social, religious and economic transformation of the people. As far as the form and technique of the novel is concerned Rao makes a deliberate attempt to follow traditional Indian narrative technique and foreground the Indian sensibility that pervades the entire village '*Kanthapura*'. He writes in the forward of the novel;

The telling has not been easy. One has to convey in a language that is not one's own the spirit that is one's own. One has to convey . . . a certain thought-movement that looks maltreated in an alien language. I use the word 'alien', yet English is not really an alien language to us. It is the language of our intellectual make-up. We are all instinctively bilingual, many of us writing in our own language and in English. We cannot write like the English. We should not. We cannot write only as Indians. We have grown to look at the large world as part of us. Our method of expression therefore has to be a dialect which will someday prove to be as distinctive and colourful as the Irish or the American. Time alone will justify it. (Rao 1938, vii)

The book has been considered by many to be the first classic modern Indian writing in English and it is considered the best *Gandhian* novels in English. In fact, both the spirit and the narrative technique of '*Kanthapura*' are primarily those of the Indian *Puranas*, which may be described as a popular encyclopaedia of medieval India. Rao at the outset describes his novel as a *sthala-purana* - legend of a place. The *Puranas* are a blend of narration, description, philosophical reflection, and religious teaching.

Kanthapura is not unique in its manipulation of the English language; during the thirties, other prominent Indian English novelists, including Mulk Raj Anand and R. K. Narayan, experimented with English too, reshaping it in various ways to approximate this or that Indian vernacular. But while these authors give little reason to consider their stylistic innovation as anything more than a creative strategy deployed for aesthetic ends (Krishnaswamy and Burde 1998, 32), Rao is clearly proposing the 'Indianized' English of *Kanthapura* as a functional model for the real, spoken English of India.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Raja Rao has enjoyed considerable attention from literary scholars in America, Britain, and the Indian subcontinent, who see in his writing perhaps the most sustained and coherent attempt to engage with some of the most politically

contentious, and therefore theoretically important, contemporary issues. Code-mixing is considered as a valuable communication tools that have intrigued researchers for quite some time. Studies have been conducted to explore the grammatical aspects of code-mixing, with a focus on identifying the points in discourse or sentences where the language switching occurs and understanding how speakers execute it

Hudson (1980) differentiated between code-switching, code-mixing and borrowing and asserted that Codeswitching was 'the inevitable consequence of bilingualism' Many aspects of code-switching and code-mixing between Hindi and English have also been studied (Chetia, 2017; Sailaja, 2011). Chetia (2017) observed that in a multilingual country like India, code-mixing and code-switching have become a norm rather than a deviation. Studies have also been carried out in the fields of advertisements, TV shows, and Bollywood movies (Kathpalia, 2015; Herring, 2003; Mónica, 2009; Sailaja, 2011).

Objective and Methodology

The review of the literature shows that extensive research has been done in code-switching and code-mixing in almost all genres and contexts. They have been explored in Indian English fiction as well though a close and in-depth analysis of these communicative tools is yet to be conducted. The current paper thus aims to analyze the role of code-mixing in indigenous interpersonal communicative contexts in Indian English fiction. This novel '*Kanthapura* (1938) has been examined by researchers from different perspectives like the colonial and post-colonial India and the Role of Code-Switching and Code-Mixing in mobilizing populist resistance and reaching out to different segments of the society by cultural and religious means.

The prolonged contact between English and Indian languages, and its use by Indians with varied linguistic background and varying levels of competence in English, has resulted in it been '*Indianised*' in as much as there have been phonological and morpho-syntactic adjustments in English, adjustments that can be attributed to the influence of Indian languages and culture. This nativization or mother tongue word influence while writing in another language has now become the feature of their writing, but over a period of time this interference variety has accorded typical status and flavour to Indian English..

Analysis of the data

The code-mixed words are categorized under their suitable titles will help us to understand the meaning of code-mixed words, phrases and expressions with reference to the text. Their explanations are given below with the examples.

1. Names

In the novel '*Kanthapura*' there are so many personas with distinctive names which function not only their names but they also disclose their profession and character too. In the below example names of the mountains and passes are given to describe the landscape of the '*Kanthapura*' with lucidity and vividly

Roads, narrow, dusty, rut-covered roads, wind through the forests of teak and of jack, of sandal and of sal, and hanging over bellowing gorges and leaping over elephant-haunted valleys, they turn now to the left and now to the right and bring you through the Alambe and Champa and Mena and Kola passes into the great granaries of trade. (p.7)

Alambe and '*Champa*' and '*Mena*' and "*Kola*" are the names of mountains, which are situated in the Village of *Kanthapura*". The road to this village was going through these mountains. It was a very important road for the villagers as well as for Red-men because; it was the main link through which they were trading with villagers. Though road was narrow and dusty but when the carts were passing through the '*Mena*' and '*Kola*' mountains, it dramatically described the landscape of the village.

b)"When the rice is husked and washed and is nothing but pulp, they sell it to *BanyaRamanlal* or *Chotalal*, who send it by train to *BanyaBapanlal* and *Motilal*..." (p.24)

The word *Banya* is a Hindi /Urdu word which means a trader who deals with the selling and buying of rice. These traders are called by their typical names in the society like above *Ramanlal*, *Chotalal*, *Bapanlal*, and *Motilal*. In this example the villagers of *Kanthapura* sell their rice at the cheap rates when it is just pulp to the *BanyaRamanlal* or *Chotalal*, who then send it by train to *BanyaBapanlal* and *Motilal* whom then sent to it *Tippur* fair.

Profession

Code-mixing takes place when an attempt is made to highlight the profession in relation to the society or class in which he/she works. In '*Kanthapura*' *Suryanarya* and *Nanjundia* are known by their professions which is a typical characteristic of rural India.

a) "Our village had four and twenty houses. Not all were big like Postmaster Suryanarya's double-storied house by the Temple Corner. But some were really not bad to look at. Our PatwariNanjundia had a veranda with two rooms built onto the old house".(p9)

In the above sentences, we have two code mixed words the first is 'Postmaster *Suryanarya*' and the second '*PatwariNanjundia*'. They are not only the names of characters but they also show their profession too. The first we have '*Postmaster Suryanarya*' who collects letters from the post office and then distributes them to their respective place. The second we have '*PatwariNanjundia*' who is a state functionary in the Revenue Collection system. 'Patwari' is a Hindi word used in the sub-continent for a land record clerk in a tehsil or sub-Division. In both the examples their names are associated with their professions, which is a typical feature of Indian culture.

In 'Kanthapura' certain character are not only known by their names but of their professions like Trumpet Lingayya.

b)"Trumpet Lingayya with his silver trumpet was always there, and once the music was over, we stayed till the camphor was lit, and throwing a last glance at the god, we went home to sleep, with the god's face framed within our eyes". (P. 14)

Trumpet Lingayya is the name of character in the novel. Who plays trumpet in the temple whenever there is any religious or Cultural celebration in the village. Lingayya was famous in the village not by his name but of his silver Trumpet which was also his profession.

There is another character in the novel whose name is advocate Ramaswamy. He is very famous among the villagers because he charges less fees.

"The Three- Pice Advocate as they used to call him, and he was as good as any other."(p.3 1)

In this example of Code-mixing the name shows typical Indian sensibility where names are associated with their fee, and profession.

Physical deficiency

Code-mixing also takes place when we describe physical condition of a person. In 'Kanthapura' we have so many characters who are called and known only because of their physical deficiencies. These are the minor characters who are not known by their names but of their physical deficiencies which is a typical characteristic of Indian rural societies.

a)" Left- handed Madanna's son Chenna, and Beadle Timmayya's son Bhima, and old Mota and one-eyed Linga and Jack-TreeTippa, all of them follow him home, and to each one of them he gives a spinning. "(p.26)

Left- handed *Madanna's* son *Chenna*, *Beadle Timmayya's* son *Bhima*, old *Mota*, one-eyed Linga and *Jack-Tree Tippa* all have distinctive physical identities in the village. People call them with their physical defects particularly in the rural areas of India, where it becomes their nick name also.

b) "There was also that Bent- legged Chandrayya. He died god knows how, but they found him in the garden, dead."(p.54)

Bent- legged *Chandrayya* is a minor character in the novel, whose name gives us extra information about his physical condition. In this example of code mixing, Chandrayya a cardamom- garden coolie died mysteriously in the garden, but some people were saying that he died of flying snakes bite, which had earlier killed many coolies in the garden.

Habit

In the 'Kanthapura' Code-mixing takes place when a habit of a person is associated with his name. Nanjamma a minor character in the novel is known her habit of nose - scratching.

a) "And it was Moorthy who came to the Brahmin Street, says he to Nose scratching Nanjamma, sister, the congress is giving away free spinning-wheels. (p.23)

Location

In 'Kanthapura' code-mixing takes place when the address of a particular place, field, or shop is described. Narsamma is the old widowed mother of Moorthy and her house is situated at the corner of the village.

"Corner- house Narsamma's son Moorthy- we always called him- was going through our backyard one day and, seeing a half- sunk linga, said, 'why not unearth it and wash it and consecrate it" (P. 13)

In this example of Code mixing, Corner house Narsamma is not only the name of a house and it also gives us extra information about the house owner.

Title or Social status

Title is a prefix or suffix added to a person's name to signify either veneration, an Official position or a professional or academic qualification. In some languages, titles may even be inserted between a first and last name. Social status, titles are Inevitable part of every culture. Raja Rao's 'Kanthapura' is also full of such names identify classes and the people who have special position in the rural society

"Clever fellow this Bhatta! One day he was sure to become the zamindar of the whole village—though we all knew him walking about the streets with only a loin-cloth about him." (p. 11)

Zamindar' is an Urdu word means landlord. In the sub- continent, it were the Mughals, who first made them official employees to collect taxes from peasants. In this example Bhatta, the first Brahmin in the village and whose primary job was to religion but instead of that he adds several acres of the peasant's lands to domain. This particular example shows the socio-economic division of the village through code mixing.

"...the first house you saw was the nine beamed house of Patel Range Gowda." (P. 12)

'Patel' is a Kannada word means 'head' or 'chief. In this example Range Gowda is a man of forceful, commanding personality and wields considerable power and authority in the village. Because of his forceful personality and determination he is also known as the 'Tiger' of the village. In this example the status of a character is shown through the example of code mixing.

Festivals

Every society follows some customs and festivals which become its specific identity. Indian Festivals celebrated by varied cultures through their special rituals add to the colours of Indian Heritage. In the novel there are so many festivals which constitute cultural values of the south Indian In this example of code mixing Chandrayya made pots for the Gauri's festival and Manjarpur fair.

a)"But Chandrayya still made festival pots, and for Gauri's festival we have always had our pots done by him. He makes our images too and he even sold them at the Manjarpur fair." (p.12)

Gauri'is the name of a Hindu deity. Chandrayya is a minor character in the novel.a potter living in the small potter's street and makes clay pots and sells them On the *Gauri* festivals, *Manjampur* fair where people are buying these pots for special religious purposes Herein this example Moorthy is talking to his aunt about these festivals which he personally wanted to celebrate them in the village..

Religion

Some examples in the novel 'Kanthapura' vividly displayed the religion conventions in Indian culture. The religious sentiments of the rural folk were fully exploited like when B.G. Tilak introduced the *Ganapati* festival in and instilled courage, patriotism, discipline and unity among people. In this example *Kenchamma* is the presiding deity of the village and the villager's full faith in her.

a)"Kenchamma protected virtue and destroyed evil. She would work like the way of Dhama.. ." (p.37)
The goddess is a symbol of security or protection for the people of 'Kanthapura', whatever may be the circumstances. 'Dhama' is a Hindi word means religion and it's also the name of a character in the Ramayana who was a brave fighter.

Cuisine

In the 'Kanthapura' many Indian cuisines are mentioned in general and south Indian cuisines in particular like Vermicelli, *Paysama* etc.

"For midday meal he will have a Vermicelli Paysama and patwari Nanjundia and his son-in-law are both invited there." (p. 10)

'Vermicelli' is a type of pasta and it is made from durum wheat. In India vermicelli has many names like *Shemai* in Bengali, *Seviyan* in Hindi and Urdu, *Sev* in Gujarati, *'Shavige'* in Kannada. *'Payasam'* is a south Indian dish and it is served and relished from the flat banana leaf instead of cups after *'rasam'* rice and it is also offered to the gods during rituals and ceremonies.

In this example there was a ceremony going on in the Brahmin quarter and variety of dishes have been prepared.

b)"Then the real obsequial dinner begins, with fresh honey and solid curds, and Bhatta's beloved Bengal- gram Khir."(P.28)

kheer or '*Khir*' is a traditional South Asian sweet dish, made by boiling rice or broken wheat with milk and sugar, and flavoured with cardamoms, raisins, saffron, pistachios or almonds. In this example of code mixing, there is a ceremony going on in the Brahmin quarter, but everybody is waiting for the real obsequial dinner in which different varieties have been prepared among one is the Bengal- gram *Khir*.

Clothes

Clothes also have important social and cultural functions, as we see in the novel *Kanthapura*. In this example a Sari and a gold trinket is offered to the goddess. *Kenchamma*, who is the presiding deity of the village.

a) "We gave a Sari and a gold Trinket to the goddess, and the goddess never touched those that are to live- as for the old ones, they would have died one way or the other anyway."(p.8)

A sari or saree is a female garment in the Indian Subcontinent. In this example of code mixing a Sari and a gold trinket is offered to the goddess *Kenchamma*, presiding deity of the village. It is she who saves them from the Cholera or the small pox. Thus, the villagers had a deep faith on the goddess *Kenchamma*.

CONCLUSION

It is observed that code mixing is a universal phenomenon and highlights languages in contact. It is revealed that code mixing is a common feature of Indian English. The novel under consideration has depicted India and its socio-political condition, when it was under the British occupation. To study Indian writing in English by using code mixing will be very helpful and interesting for the students. The novel under consideration is full of many themes like the encounter between East and West, the socio-political condition, casteism, Indian myths, and Impact of *Gandhian* movement on a south Indian village, religious conservatism and social uplift.

Rao incorporates many of its nativized features into his creative dialect—especially morphological and syntactical features—while giving them a more distinctly Indian lexical texture. His agenda, in the main, seems to have been to make IE more overtly 'culture-bound in the socio-cultural setting of India' (Kachru 1966, 410)

The process of cross-culturization and linguistic exchange of English has been going on for approximately last four centuries. Now it has entered the intra-linguistic and intra-cultural phase of development. It is evident from the fact that writers are able to create internationally acclaimed literature in Indian English. The sociolinguistic approach to the Indian English is to be useful for understanding the piece of work. By using this strategy; it enhances our understanding of our society and culture.

The research has shown India's multilingual society and cultural diversity. People in India have been using more than one language in the form of loan words in their daily conversations. It is observed that bilingual or multilingual speakers living in the pluralistic societies use code mixing frequently.

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